

instant city, a music building game table

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Biographical information

Sibylle Hauert & Daniel Reichmuth

Since 1999, Sibylle Hauert and Daniel Reichmuth work together as artists and performer in the field of new media installation and research with an educational and training background in theatre, music and electrical engineering. Since 2000, they have worked on self-built electronic systems in connection with developable creative software programs to stage and provoke real movement and sensual perception through electronic installations or performative “TOOLS”.

Volker Böhm

Born 1971, he studied “Audiodesign” at the Electronic Studio, Music-Academy Basel by Wolfgang Heiniger and Thomas Kessler and School Music and Music Theorie at the Music Academie Freiburg. Since 2004 he is head master of the course “Audiodesign” at the Electronic Studio, Music-Academy Basel. He lives and works as musician, programmer and audiodesigner in Basel.

Description of Piece

instant city is many things at the same time: an interactive computer game, an unpredictable music instrument, a theatrical social game, a psychological test, a light sculpture, a conversation space, an aesthetic testing field... Yet even when the various aspects of instant city can be named, through its own art and means, this music building game automat brings a dynamic impulse into space that is new and whose true quality has over and over again approved.

One or more players at a table can create architecture using semi-transparent building blocks and in the process make different modular compositions audible.

Every performance is unique because the sequence, timing and combination possibilities are completely in the hands of the players!

For each game one composition is chosen.

To date, ten different musicians have each produced special compositions which serve as the basic music building kits of instant city.

www.instantcity.ch